

EFFECT OF CYCLE NUMBER ON FATIGUE OF CONCRETE COLUMNS REINFORCED BY NON-ADHESIVE FILAMENT WOUND COMPOSITES

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1 General Introduction

The purpose of this paper is to study compression after fatigue (CAF) strength of concrete columns reinforced by filament wound glass/epoxy composites. The columns are fatigued by compression between 0 kg loading and peak loading of 19300 kg with various fatigue cycles of N=1000, 2000, 3000, 4000, and 5000. A compression test is then conducted on the columns to evaluate CAF strength, and the failure modes are also observed. The load-displacement curves of some specific fatigue cycles are recorded to obtain the hysteresis curves. CAF strength of composite/concrete columns is 53.6% higher than that of concrete columns. This shows that the excellent fatigue strength on the concrete columns is provided by the glass/epoxy composite jackets.

Under the action of repeated traffic overloading or chemical attacks, the civil infrastructures are prone to cause some degradation in their stiffness and loading behavior, and the FRP composites have proved to increase the stiffness and ultimate strength of the strengthened reinforced concrete (RC) beams and columns. Yet, the long-term effect of the FRP retrofit on civil infrastructures under fatigue and environmental effects is a major concern for the acceptability of FRP retrofit technology. Circular bridge piers can be reinforced by wound composites, which provide circumferential confinement and increase compressive strength [1,2]. A pre-fabricated filament wound composite tube with encased concrete core has proved to have better axial load capacity and corrosion resistance [3]. The adhesion bonding between the concrete beam and composite plate can increase the bending stiffness of a concrete beam; however, this adhesive bonding may reduce the compression after impact (CAI) strengths of

concrete columns reinforced by FRP jackets. It is because that the shear stress transfer at the composite/concrete interface becomes the weakest link during impact test and thereafter reduces the confining effect [4]. By inserting two layers of aluminum foil between the concrete surface and filament wound composite to form a non-adhesive filament winding process, Liu et al. [5] were able to exclude this weakest link and achieved a better CAI strength. For stress amplitude less than the threshold value, 1/3 of the compression strength of the plain concrete column, the CAF strength reduction of composite/concrete columns is less than 5% [6].

2 Results and Discussion

The composite/concrete column was fabricated by the two-axis filament winding machine as shown in figure 1. The concrete column with dimension of diameter 10 cm and length 20 cm is served as the mandrel during the winding process. Glass rovings were soaked through epoxy resin bath and wound onto concrete column under a certain tension. During the process, two layers of aluminum foils are inserted between the glass/epoxy and the concrete column to conduct a non-adhesive filament winding process. Winding angle of $[\pm 45]_3$ has been adopted in this study to wind six layers of glass roving onto the concrete columns. After the filament winding process, the composite/concrete columns were put on a rotational frame and then placed in a furnace to conduct a specially designed curing process. To simulate the situation of a concrete column subjected to repeated traffic overloading, a low cycle, and high stress amplitude fatigue test is performed. To study the effect of fatigue cycle on the compression after fatigue (CAF) strength of both concrete and composite/concrete systems, five kinds of fatigue cycles, 1000, 2000, 3000, 4000, and 5000 are

selected in performing the fatigue tests, while the fatigue stress amplitude kept the same. The columns are subjected to fatigue loading between σ_{\max} (compressive stress) and σ_{\min} (equals zero), and fatigue stress amplitude is defined as " $\sigma_{\max} - \sigma_{\min}$ ". Thus, the compressive fatigue stress amplitude is 24.1MPa. An MTS-810 testing machine with axial compressive capacity of 25 ton is used to perform the fatigue test.

CAF results for concrete (FC-N) and composite/concrete columns (WFC-N) are shown in figure 2. Percentage CAF strength of both columns reduces as the number of fatigue cycle increases. However, it can be cleared seen that the curve for WFC-N (round data) is more flat than that of FC-N (square data), indicating that composite/concrete columns can retain their residual strengths after larger number of fatigue cycles. It has to be noted that percentage CAF strength at 5000 fatigue cycles for both concrete and composite/concrete columns are respectively 29.5 MPa and 45.4 MPa. The latter is 53.6% higher than the former. The result shows that the composite/concrete column has better fatigue performance than pure concrete column.

Fig. 1 The schematic of the filament winding process to fabricate composite/concrete columns

Fig. 2 The Correlation between CAF and fatigue cycles for concrete and concrete reinforced by composites

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